

EXPLORING KINDNESS AND EMPATHY IN AN ORIGINAL CHILDREN'S BOOK

by

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Abstract

It is common for people to remember a certain children's book - often fiction - they read when they were younger. This is the power of narratives and books to leave a lasting impression on people. As a future elementary school teacher, I see the importance of educating children about relevant concepts that are critical to the development of their character. With this in mind, I decided to create an original children's book that focuses on the concepts of kindness and empathy, and that targets children between the ages of five and seven, though I believe anyone can benefit from reading this book. To create this book, I developed a detailed storyboard to guide my creative process of writing the story and drawing digital illustrations to accompany my text. The fictional story follows a young girl's journey to making friends as she endures hardships and loneliness along the way because she feels and is perceived as different, and it is through kindness and empathy that she overcomes these difficulties and creates lasting friendships. My book is inspired by existing literature that spreads messages about these two concepts, and it is also motivated by my passion for bringing more kindness into the world because there continues to be a need for this. The overall goal and purpose of this project is to creatively explore the true meaning of kindness and empathy and inspire readers to apply these ideas to their everyday lives.

Introduction

Kindness and empathy are fundamental concepts to teach children from an early age, especially in today's world, which is deeply tainted by hate and discrimination. Educating them about what is and is not acceptable thinking and behavior are crucial to building strong ethical character. Early childhood is pivotal to child development because this is the age when children take in information from the world around them and use their learned experiences to shape the foundation for their ways of thinking and acting in future years. This makes it essential to teach children about the importance of kindness and empathy so that they can truly grasp these concepts and actively make them a part of their daily lives. Reading is one of the strong and appealing ways through which children can be educated in an understandable manner, and this inspired my work in writing and illustrating an original children's book, titled *Fifi Finds Friends*, that focused on kindness and empathy. My purpose for this project is to address these two topics through a medium that is recognized for its ability to make lasting impacts on children's lives. I am pursuing a career in elementary education, and thus, my work was also motivated by my desire to teach future generations about these matters so that they can implement kind practices into their daily lives. The importance of kindness and empathy can be effectively communicated to children through fictional stories due to the well-known power of narrative books to convey complex issues in an engaging and accessible manner, to incorporate both animal and human characters to demonstrate differences in metaphorical ways that are not overly explicit, and to develop visual literacy skills in children.

Storyline Summary

A young girl named Fifi lives in a forest where she is the only human. She often spends her days drawing or picking strawberries and mushrooms to make her favorite meal. There are four animals living in the forest with her: Bear, Wolf, Rabbit, and Wolf. They are all friends with each other but not with Fifi. As the only human, Fifi is very different from the others, which makes them to be afraid of her and to have misconceptions about her. Consequently, Fifi experiences much loneliness and sadness because she is always trudging around the forest alone while she sees the four of them together. Although Fifi is afraid of them, she makes an effort to express her interest in them by drawing some of them while hiding behind a tree and setting out the strawberries she picks for them to take. As a symbol of her friendliness towards them and a small act of kindness, she adds sketches of flowers and butterflies to her drawings of them because she observes that they like them. It is ultimately through the power of kindness and empathy expressed through art and acts of generosity that Fifi, Bear, Wolf, Rabbit, and Bird come together as friends. The animals decide to take the first step in befriending Fifi after Wolf finds her drawings of Bear and himself and realizes that she likes them. He also sees her crying alone, which unlocks a special memory and leads him to empathize with Fifi. Through these drawings, the five characters are able to connect with each other through a medium that expresses Fifi's interest in the friends nonverbally. The story ends with an open ending that leaves readers with the message that kindness and empathy are an attitude that does not disappear after one encounter. Kindness and empathy should become part of an individual's character and guide their actions.

Creative Process: Methodology

All the creative work for the book was done digitally. The primary tool that I used to write my story and draw by illustrations was an iPad. I used two main apps on the iPad for this project. The first was Procreate, an app I learned to use for this project. With it, I created all my illustrations for the book. To do so, I worked with many brushes, tools, and layers to create sketches and color my images. Each time I completed a drawing, I exported it into the second app I utilized for this project, which was Goodnotes. I was more familiar with this app and the tools it offered. The primary function of this app was to compile all my illustrations and text in one place. I created custom pages that measured eight by eleven inches to match the size of my printed, physical book. On each page, I exported each illustration and resized them to an appropriate size that left enough room for the text. After adding the illustration, I added a text box and typed out the accompanying writing for each page. The same process was used for the front and back cover of my book. I also used Goodnotes in the early stages of my project to create digital storyboards. The main storyboard I used outlined the contents of each page of the book. It included a detailed description and breakdown of the plot for each page, which then guided what my illustrations would look like. Early in the process, I also created a second digital storyboard to sketch out basic ideas and the layout for some of the pages before beginning on the actual illustrations.

Creative Process: General Choices for My Book

My decision to create a fictional story stemmed from the widely recognized power of reading and, in particular, of reading fiction books. Reading continues to be an important source of knowledge, and it is both taught and strongly enforced in the education system because literacy is essential for success in various areas of life apart from academics. Children acquire knowledge from the books that they read, and ethical development is one of these areas that reading targets. In particular, the genre of fiction provides a wide range of benefits to children in the areas of emotional and ethical development (Cain 69; Kleji et al. 2; Mustafayevich 38). Fiction books can effectively convey messages to children by growing their understanding of others' feelings. This type of understanding is possible because literary fiction allows readers to be engaged in realistic and relatable social interactions and experiences that inspire connections between characters and young readers (Mustafayevich 39). Fiction books use images and words to convey the characters' emotions, thoughts, and feelings, which aid in children's understanding of the stories presented to them (Kucirkova 8). The conflicts and challenges that the characters face in these stories tap into the reader's own experiences, which results in an increase in the ability to be empathetic towards others they encounter like they can empathize with the characters in the books they read (Cain 69). Even when readers cannot directly relate to the

experiences detailed in these stories, literary fiction allows readers to grow their knowledge of different people's lives and feelings, which in turn can inspire empathy. By reading and engaging with these experiences, children practice being aware of the various experiences and feelings that others can go through (Kucirkova 8). As a result, readers have greater self-reported empathy from reading fiction (Cain 69). Also, children feel that group cooperation and independent thinking exert a stronger influence on their ethical understanding rather than authoritarian approaches from adults (Cain 70). This explains why books with relatable characters are a productive means of communicating important lessons and information to children as opposed to strictly instructing them what to do. Simply telling children to think and act a certain way toward others is not sufficient and lacks in comparison to having them read books about topics such as kindness and empathy.

Moreover, my decision to specifically focus on kindness and empathy as the overarching themes of the book originated from the fact that children's literature that encourages these concepts is important to combat discriminatory practices and thinking. As mentioned earlier, a child's early years are a crucial period in their development, so introducing them to these topics during this period is critical and beneficial. In fact, the effects of incorporating children's literature into California classrooms to discuss topics related to racism and diversity have recently been examined (Spencer 15). The study took place during the 2020 to 2021 academic year and involved eight teachers actively working in a school. Upon debriefing with these teachers on their experiences, it was found that having these books in their classroom library allowed children to freely speak and question details about the world around them through open conversations (Spencer 21). Bringing books that discussed diversity and inclusion sparked natural conversations about differences and similarities between the children and the characters

in the stories (Spencer 21). Allowing them to physically see images of all types of people was an important way for children to respectfully inquire about the differences that they saw and understand that the world was filled with many groups of individuals (Spencer 22). Children are aware that differences between people do exist, and this understanding develops into curiosity that children's books allow them to explore. Curiosity is an epistemic emotion, which means that it leads to knowledge acquisition and generation. Engaging with this type of literature allows children to have their questions answered in a courteous manner. Reading about characters that are like them allow children to feel seen and represented, while reading about differences can inspire children to be kind and inclusive of all people.

Additionally, to communicate the themes of kindness and empathy in my fiction book, I decided to create a storyline that involves animals and a human, which is grounded in a tradition of literature that incorporates anthropomorphism into the plot. Anthropomorphism refers to the assigning of human abilities and qualities to animals, and children's literature featuring this concept often leave a strong impression on readers (Burke and Copenhagen 206). In fact, when asked by teachers about powerful literature they have read, students point to books that possess a tie to the real world (Burke and Copenhagen 206). In other words, the stories present scenarios or experiences they have seen in their lives and can relate to them. It has been noted that many of these books cited by students involve animal characters (Burke and Copenhagen 206). Animals communicate using the human language in children's literature to show that they are not as different from humans as they are often made out to be (Le Guin 22). Some individuals throughout history have tried to reduce animals to creatures that do not have emotions, thoughts, or the ability to communicate because they do not live exactly the way that humans do. However, animals and humans can communicate with each other in nonverbal ways, so writers try to bring

this point across by creating animals that can speak through meaningful sounds, words, or body language (Le Guin 23). Books have the potential to exert lifelong impacts on young minds, so weaving in lessons into the storyline with animals can be very influential. Thus, apart from the value in using animal characters that can talk, books that present animals in this way are valuable because they allow children to be exposed to important societal issues in a manner that does not come off as aggressive or overly instructive (Burke and Copenhaver 210). Some of these societal issues fall under the topics of race, respecting differences, and morals (Burke and Copenhaver 211). These benefits influenced my choice to create an original children's book that made use of non-human animals that interacted with a human to help children comprehend and remember the importance of being kind and empathetic to everyone.

Creative Process: Storyline

Upon my decision to include both non-human animals and a human character, I drew inspiration from existing children's books that incorporated anthropomorphism. The first book I was inspired by was *It Will Be Ok* by Lisa Katzenberger. In this story, the author employed the characters Giraffe and Zebra to convey the importance of understanding the feelings of others, supporting others in times of need, and overcoming one's fears to befriend those that are different. Giraffe was initially afraid of another character named Spider, and Giraffe was unable to come down from a tree because he saw Spider. Zebra reassured Giraffe that his feelings were completely valid and waited patiently until Giraffe was ready to come down. Giraffe eventually overcame his fear and even mustered up the courage to ask Spider to join them on their journey after he saw Spider walking alone. The story concluded with Giraffe and Zebra both empathizing with Spider's fear of them as they waited for Spider under the same tree that Giraffe once stood on. An important element of my original story was the way fear stopped individuals from making

an effort to befriend others that were different from them, which Katzenberger also emphasized in her book.

The second book I was inspired by was *Koala Is Not a Bear* by Kristin L. Gray. This author emphasized the power of kindness by taking the reader through the experiences of Koala who was warmly welcomed to the bear cabin by Grizzly upon her arrival at a camp. Koala experienced an identity crisis because Kangaroo repeatedly claimed that she should not be in the bear cabin because she was not a bear despite Grizzly continuously defending her. Koala began to feel that she did not belong entirely, but soon Koala and Kangaroo discovered that they shared more in common than they would have ever thought. By the end of the story, Koala found where she belonged, and all the animals happily embraced one another. The book had an open ending with a new animal introduced, which foreshadowed that the other animals would empathize with them as a result of what happened to Koala. A crucial element of my story that the characters discovered towards the end was that they too shared some similarities with each other despite their differences, and this helped unite them closer. My story, like Gray's story, also included an open ending that let readers envision what would happen with the introduction of a new character that resembled the main character in their struggles before finding friends.

The third work of inspiration for my book was *Not Quite Narwhal* by Jessie Sima. Sima used the story of Kelp, a unicorn who believed he was a narwhal, who was kindly accepted by other narwhals despite his differences. He embarked on an unexpected journey to the ocean's shore where he found creatures that looked like him. These unicorns happily welcomed Kelp and even taught him all about their unique unicorn skills. Though Kelp was nervous about being accepted by the narwhals upon his return to the ocean, his fears were washed away when his friends welcomed him and took the news of his self-discovery very well. All ended well in the

story as Kelp was able to bring together his narwhal and unicorn friends and live joyfully while spending time with both groups of friends. An important plot point in my story was each character having their own unique activity they enjoyed doing, which set them apart from the others. The main character's love for drawing was what ultimately brought all the characters together in harmony and led all five characters to teach each other about the activities they found joy in like the animals in Sima's book.

The fourth book I drew inspiration from was *Share Some Kindness Bring Some Light* by Apryl Stott. Stott used both animals and a human character to stress what true kindness and empathy were like. Coco, a young girl, and Bear both admired each other's kindness, and they sought to show the other animals in the story that Bear was kind because they assumed she was mean and scary. Coco was consistently empathetic towards Bear and stuck by her side to make Bear feel better and reassured. She even helped Bear make cookies for the other animals to spread kindness to those around her. Bear was afraid of talking to the other animals at first, but Coco reassured her that it was okay to feel this way as long as she did not let fear get in the way of spreading kindness. All the animals declined Bear's thoughtful gift which discouraged her. On the way home, Coco and Bear found Baby Deer in trouble, and Bear kindly extended her hand so Baby Deer could ride on her back. Ultimately, the other animals recognized Bear's true, kind heart as a result of her actions, and Bear also learned that true kindness was all about giving love without expecting anything in return. As mentioned before, fear was a significant part of my story and was used to convey the idea that making wrongful assumptions about others that were different was harmful. Fear of the unknown acts as a barrier against kindness and empathy but working toward overcoming this fear makes way for kindness and empathy to shine through as they did in Stott's story.

Creative Process: Characters

From the various outlets of inspiration, I created five characters to convey the message of the importance of kindness and empathy. Instead of having all non-human animal characters, I felt that having one human among them would highlight the differences between these characters and elevate the tension that existed amongst them. The overall color palette of the book was made up of various shades of pink. To fit this color palette, I chose to make all the characters with warm colors. In general, they were made up of pink, orange, and yellow.

My first character was Fifi, who was also the protagonist of the story. I chose to portray her as a young girl to fit with the targeted age level for the book so that readers could form a connection with her and perhaps even see themselves in her character. Fifi was given a very animated and pink appearance to encapsulate her innocence and approachability. I also characterized her as loving the color pink to explain the way she presented herself and her surroundings such as her house. Her bright outward appearance complemented her kind nature.

My second character was Bear. He was the biggest of all the characters since bears are naturally larger creatures. Bear is a coral color to go with the palette of the book. I also used

warmer and brighter colors for all the non-human animal characters to convey a sense of warmth in the reader. As established, Fifi's favorite color was also pink, so I wanted to make most of the animals a shade of pink or a color that coordinated with pink as a form of union amongst all the characters despite their individual differences. Throughout the book, I made Bear have strong expressions to mimic the way bears might appear in nature. I also drew him to be standing on two feet to incorporate the concept of anthropomorphism and the idea that animals and humans could interact with one another because they were similar.

My third character was Rabbit. She was drawn to be a pink color to fit the book's color scheme as indicated previously. Rabbit was one of the smaller animals because I wanted to have two bigger, frightening animals and two smaller, more approachable animals. I believed that having this contrast would draw attention to the other two animals. This was an important detail because one of them played a key role in the turning point of the story.

My fourth character was Wolf. I wanted to include one character that was not traditionally perceived as approachable because of their appearance so that I could use the reader's existing perceptions toward this animal to demonstrate the concept of empathy to a greater degree. Bears could be seen as scary, but people tended to admire them more than they admired wolves. To encapsulate this, I always drew one tooth sticking out of Wolf's mouth to convey this fierceness. At the same time, he is also drawn to be a light blush color. Like Bear, I drew him to be one of the two more frightening, non-human animal characters because he was the reason for the twist and key plot point in the story.

The fifth and final character of my book was Bird. I drew her to be the smallest and also one of the more approachable animals. Like Rabbit, Bird acted like a supporting character to the story like Rabbit. Although they are also important to the story, the focus occasionally shifted to Bear and Wolf during major points of the plot. Bird is drawn to be a bright yellow color to go

along with the overall theme of warm colors in the book and to show that even the animals that appeared smaller and welcoming were too startling for Fifi to approach.

Creative Process: Illustrations

In terms of the illustrations, I drew all the characters in a sketchy style as if created using traditional pencil and paper. There were two main reasons for this stylistic choice. The first reason was that since this book is intended for young children to read, I believed it would be fitting to create illustrations that were not too complex and would also align with my own level of skill in drawing. The second reason was that sketching and drawing were important elements of the plot. From the beginning of the story, it was established that Fifi had a love for drawing. It was her drawings of the other characters that symbolized Fifi's early acts of kindness towards them and pushed the four animals to make an effort to befriend Fifi. Art served as a unifying element in the story and allowed the five characters to connect with one another. Thus, it felt suitable to incorporate the idea of sketching and drawing into the book's illustrations. With this in mind, the illustrations were intentionally drawn imperfectly in the sense that some of the lines were not perfectly straight, round, or connected with adjacent lines. Similarly, the coloring of the illustrations was also imperfect to portray this sketchy drawing style.

Apart from the drawing style of the illustrations, there were other important artistic choices I made. Most of the illustrations did not cover the entire page of the book and color did not take up the entire page because I did not want to draw too much attention away from the text.

There were only four pages out of forty-two where color covered the whole page, and this was intentional. The first page that I chose to do this was on page six. Here, Wolf was drawn without any of the other three animals. I purposely gave this page a completely different background to foreshadow that Wolf would be a key character later in the story. The dark background contrasted starkly with the white backgrounds of the previous five pages to subtly set him apart from the other characters. Moreover, the illustration and color filled up the entire page to draw strong attention to Wolf's character from the beginning of the story. I used this same technique on pages eighteen and nineteen. At this point of the plot, the story reached the climax where the problem was soon to be resolved through Wolf's role in the story. After all, it was Wolf who first empathized with Fifi and displayed kindness towards her by trying to understand her feelings and talk his friends into joining him in inviting her to spend time together. Thus, the background mirrored that of page six as it was dark and full of color to highlight Wolf's significance in the story. Page thirty-two was the final page with color covering the entire background. Here, Fifi was drawn smiling inside of her house holding her sketchbook after she just settled plans to spend time with Bear, Wolf, Rabbit, and Bird. I chose to fill in the entire background with color and drawings because this too marked an important point in the story, the moment when Fifi and the animals finally conversed after being afraid of each other. From this point on, the relationship between the five of them changed, marking a step towards resolution.

Experience

The experience of creating *Fifi Finds Friends* was full of valuable opportunities and challenges. Since I was creating an original children's book, I had a lot of creative freedom, which brought about both difficulties and benefits. It was certainly challenging to find a starting point at the beginning of the creative process, but I knew that I wanted to center my story around kindness and another concept that went hand-in-hand with it. Through an insightful conversation with my mentor, I settled on empathy as the second theme of my book because I believed that these two concepts were vital to teach children and connected with each other. As an individual who took a few art classes as a child but never pursued art in a serious manner, this project gave me the opportunity to put my imagination to the test. From creating the characters and setting, to developing a detailed plot, each element of the book involved a great level of creativity.

Therefore, I enjoyed the creative freedom that the project gave me despite the initial struggles to establish the foundation for my illustrations and storyline.

Outcomes

There were several valuable outcomes for this project. One of the greatest results of this project was diving deep into the concepts of kindness and empathy. Before beginning to develop a detailed plot for my book, I began the creative process by conducting research on these topics, which guided my thinking and creative process. I dedicated a lot of time to creating the plot because I carefully mapped out ways that I could integrate kindness and empathy into various aspects of the plot and craft a cohesive story. The goal was to incorporate explicit examples of kindness and empathy that demonstrated what these concepts looked like in action so that children would be able to understand the deep meaning of these concepts. As a future elementary school teacher, I felt strongly about the importance of kindness and empathy in children's lives and in the classroom. As a result of my research and greater understanding of these concepts through the creation of an original book, I will be able to model these qualities in the classroom, which is important because children learn by seeing. Demonstrating kindness and empathy towards my students and colleagues can inspire my students to exhibit these values as well. In my future profession and endeavors, I will be equipped with valuable tools to show kindness and empathy to children in various circumstances. When students are experiencing rough patches, I can approach these situations with empathy by trying to understand each child's situation and considering all factors that may be affecting them. It is crucial to act kindly and empathetically towards students to create a safe learning environment where they are unafraid to seek guidance from the teacher.

Another important outcome of this project was gaining experiencing in working with children's literature. Through my work I was able to write my own literature and analyze the works of other authors. By doing so, I grasped a better understanding of how children best learned concepts, which is beneficial because in my future classroom I can effectively choose and share children's books with my students that best support their learning and ethical development. In fact, I now have my own book that I can share with my future students to teach them about kindness and empathy. As mentioned earlier, children gain knowledge from the books that they read, and this makes reading a critical part of their learning. Developing literacy is a pivotal part of early childhood education and is a necessary skill to carry out a variety of different tasks in the classroom and greater society.

Conclusion

Altogether, there continues to be a need for children's literature that covers topics such as kindness and empathy. Children need to grasp the idea that differences between people do matter as they can be integral to their identity, but they should never be used as a basis for discrimination or prejudice. The best approach to educating children about these concepts is through fiction books because children learn from imaginative stories that engage them with the characters' journeys and experiences. By reading these stories, children develop deep emotional connections with the characters, which inspires empathy in readers. This prompted me to create the book *Fifi Finds Friends* focused on these two concepts. My goals for this project were to increase my personal knowledge about these valuable concepts on a scholarly level and create a work of fiction that offered children the opportunity to grow their awareness of these concepts and ultimately inspire them to carry out practices of kindness and empathy in their lives. I was inspired by the works of other authors on similar themes to create a storyline that encapsulated

what kindness and empathy looked like in action. From my extensive work on this project, I gained a deeper understanding of what kindness and empathy were and the various factors that came into play to prevent individuals from demonstrating these qualities all the while exercising my creativity and imagination. In the end, it is never too early to teach children about kindness and empathy, especially given the current state of the world and the advantages of engaging children with this type of literature.

My Complete Book

In a forest home to many creatures, Fifi lives alone in her little, pink cottage. She's very kind, she loves pink, and she loves drawing. Today, she's drawing a picture of a butterfly that she sees near a tree.

After drawing the butterfly, Fifi has to get some strawberries and mushrooms for dinner. She gathers her belongings and is about to go when all of a sudden she hears the sounds of footsteps!

Her heart immediately begins to beat faster and faster. Fifi quickly rushes behind a tree to not be seen.

It's Bear, Rabbit, Wolf, and Bird! As usual, they try to hide from Fifi and whisper about how strange she is.

Bird explains, "She doesn't look like any of us or like to do the things we do!"

"Plus she is always holding that weird, scary stick in her hand," Bear points out.

Rabbit says, "She can't dig tunnels like me!"

Bird says, "She can't fly like me!"

Bear says, "She can't climb trees like me!"

At this point, the animals glance nervously left and right to make sure that Fifi is nowhere to be found. They are very afraid of her because she's so different and who knows if she'd be nice to them.

Wolf says, "I don't trust Fifi. She scares me!"

From a distance, Fifi whispers to herself, "I'm going to draw so time goes by faster." She peeks her head around the tree trunk and begins to draw Bear, but it's hard for her to see well.

She notices that he seems to like flowers so she sketches some in her drawing. Just as she finishes, the animals go their separate ways. Fifi waits for them to walk away and then comes out of hiding.

Fifi lets out a sigh of relief and catches her breath. She can still feel her heart beating very quickly.

All alone again, she goes back to gathering strawberries and mushrooms to make fruit salad for dinner. The sound of the animals fade further and further away and she can hear the sound of leaves rustling in the wind.

Fifi goes home and puts some of her yummy strawberries into a basket. She wants to share them with the animals. After leaving them outside of her house, she runs into her house and peeks through her window to see if any of them will stop by, but none of them do.

The next day, the animals return to the same spot by the flowers and Fifi tries to draw them again while they whisper about her.

"This time I'm going to draw Wolf," Fifi whispers to herself.

Rabbit whispers, "Guess what! You wouldn't believe what happened to me! Earlier today I was walking by the stream when I saw a flash of pink poking through the grass. I just froze because I knew it was... FIFI!"

All the animals frown and gasp in horror!

Suddenly, Wolf is angry because he remembers someone said he had a scary face. He is upset. Wolf expresses, “Wouldn’t she be scared of my face? I’m a wolf after all... She’d probably judge me for how I look so what’s the point in trying to talk to her? Come on guys let’s just forget about her and go home.”

The next day Fifi wakes up feeling very sad because she can't find her sketchbook and is afraid she'll lose all her drawings. She quietly says to herself, "Maybe I'll feel better if go outside." Fifi decides to go on a hike to stop thinking about her troubles.

Once Fifi reaches the top of the mountain she feels better already. It's beautiful to see the whole forest from up here. She's enjoying the view until she sees a group of butterflies happily flying together. Suddenly, she remembers she's all alone and feels sad again.

“This time a hike didn’t help,” Fifi says as she sits in front of her house. Tears begin to stream down her face. From a distance Wolf is walking when he hears loud sniffles. This reminds him of how he felt when he first came to the forest.

He remembers when he was separated from his pack and didn’t have any friends because he was the only one who couldn’t stand on two feet. Wolf feels a strange connection to Fifi but he can’t put his paw on it. Wolf feels like he should do something but he’s scared. For now he runs off to find his friends.

“Hey guys. I need to tell you something. I saw Fifi crying just now. She seemed really sad. Like really sad. I’m not sure why but I feel bad. I think she might be crying because she’s always alone.”

Bear blurts out, “I don’t trust her. What if she’s trying to make you feel bad?”

Wolf takes a deep breath and says, “No, I don’t think she’s faking anything. You guys have to see these drawings I found in her sketchbook! Would someone who’d want to be mean to us do this?”

At first the animals don’t want to look because they’re still upset, but when they see the drawings they can’t help but complement Fifi’s work.

Bird exclaims, “You’re telling me Fifi drew these? How’d she draw you and Bear so well? Is this what she uses her weird, scary stick for? I love these so much!”

Wolf suggests they all go to Fifi's house to return her things and invite her to hangout together at the stream, but his friends are still worried.

Wolf reassures them and leads the way. His whole body shakes as he inches closer to Fifi's door, but he reminds himself who he is. He says, "I'm a Wolf. I'm brave!" Then, Wolf knocks on her door.

Fifi opens the door and the sight of the animals makes her freeze. Wolf takes a deep breath and says, “Hi! We just wanted to say hi and give this back to you. I found your sketchbook the other day. We think your work is amazing!”

Fifi replies, “You guys think so?” The animals all nod. “Thank you! I’m glad you liked the drawings,” Fifi says smiling.

All together the animals ask, “Want to hangout with us at the stream tomorrow?”

Excitedly, Fifi says, “I would love to!”

Afterwards, the animals leave Fifi's house full of smiles. Fifi closes her door. She is so happy! She holds her sketchbook close to her heart and says, "Wow! They're so nice! I can't believe it took so long for us to talk." With that, Fifi and the animals happily enjoy the rest of the day!

At last, the five of them meet at the stream! They sit together on a blanket with yummy snacks and smiles. Fifi shares the strawberry salad she brought for them. All the animals love it because they like strawberries and mushrooms too!

After eating, they decide to teach each other the things they like to do. First, Bear shows Fifi how to climb a tree. She is so impressed at Bear's strength because she slips down as she tries to pull herself up the trunk. Bear is still proud of her for trying!

Next, Bird shows Fifi how she reaches higher distances by flying. Fifi is so shocked at how fast Bird can flap her wings! Fifi tries to flap her arms quickly but giggles because her feet won't leave the ground.

Then, Rabbit shows Fifi how she digs tunnels in the ground to make her home. Fifi is amazed at how long Rabbit can dig without getting tired! She tries to copy Rabbit, but her arms hurt. She still makes a small hole and Rabbit is proud of her.

Finally, Wolf shows Fifi that now she has her own pack of friends. Fifi smiles. "I'm so happy to have my own kind of pack," she exclaims!

Fifi decides it's time for her to teach the animals how to draw!
She picks up her sketchbook and pencil.

Each animal gets a pencil and tries to hold it in their paw or wing. It's really tricky at first because they've never touched one before. Fifi is patient with them because she remembers having a hard time when she started drawing. They all get the hang of it eventually!

As the five of them continue to share smiles, all that Wolf, Bear, Rabbit, and Bird can think about is never letting fear stop them from making friends again! It doesn't matter if someone is different because that's what makes everyone special!

Just then, as they are all thinking of how much they love their new friends, there's a splash in the stream. Fifi, Wolf, Bear, Rabbit, and Bird see a fish alone in the water. They've never met one before or understood them. However, they smile because they already know what to do this time...

FIFI FINDS FRIENDS

A young girl named Fifi lives in a forest where she is the only human. She often spends her days drawing or picking strawberries and mushrooms to make her favorite salad. There are four animals living in the forest with her. Bear, Wolf, Rabbit, and Wolf are all friends with each other but not with Fifi. Consequently, Fifi experiences loneliness and sadness, but everything changes when Wolf finds a strange object on the forest floor one evening...

Works Cited

- Burke, Carolyn L., and Joby G. Copenhaver. "Animals as People in Children's Literature." *Language Arts*, vol. 81, no. 3, 2004, pp. 205-213. *EBSCOHost*, cdn.ncte.org/nctefiles/store/samplefiles/journals/la/la0813animals.pdf. Accessed 1 Sept. 2023.
- Cain, Melissa A. "Children's Books for Building Character and Empathy." *Journal of Invitational Theory and Practice*, vol. 21, 2015, pp. 68-94. *EBSCOHost*, login.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/login?url=https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1163013&site=ehost-live&scope=site. Accessed 12 Feb. 2022.
- Kleji, Sanne W., et al. "Reading Fiction and reading minds in early adolescence: A longitudinal study." *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, vol. 222, no. 105476, 13 June 2022, pp. 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2022.105476>. Accessed 22 Feb. 2023.
- Kucirkova, Natalia. "How Could Children's Storybooks Promote Empathy? A Conceptual Framework Based on Developmental Psychology and Literary Theory." *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 10, no. 121, 2019, pp. 1-15, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00121>. Accessed 8 Apr. 2024.
- Le Guin, Ursula K. "Cheek by Jowl: Animals in Children's Literature." *The Journal of the Association for Library Service to Children*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2004, pp. 20-30. *EBSCOHost*, <https://login.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/login?url=https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eft&AN=502932854&site=ehost-live&scope=site>. Accessed 1 Sept. 2023.
- Mustafayevich, Bayeshanov A. "Use of Fiction in the Formation of the Worldview of Youth." *Central Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, vol. 2, no. 5, 11 May 2021, pp.

37-40. <https://www.cajlpc.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJLPC/article/view/118>.

Accessed 22 Feb. 2023.

Spencer, Tamara. "Using Children's Literature to Advance Antiracist Early Childhood Teaching and Learning." *Issues in Teacher Education*, vol. 31, 2022, pp. 9-31. *EBSCOHost*, search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1362768&site=ehost-live&scope=site. Accessed 14 Feb. 2023.